

A long-awaited guest in the Bulgarian fauna, *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera), is already here

Stanislav Abadjiev¹, Mario Langourov², Nikolay Simov³

(1) [Corresponding author] National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvooboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, abadjiev@nmnhs.com

(2) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvooboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, langourov@nmnhs.com

(3) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvooboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, simov@nmnhs.com

Abstract: The first report of the migratory species *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758) from the territory of Bulgaria, from Varna, is presented. Comments on the distribution of the species, its biology, as well as illustrative material are also included.

Keywords: Bulgaria, butterfly, Danainae, migrant, new record

Introduction

Danaus chrysippus (Linnaeus, 1758) ranges from West Africa, see details in Tennent (1995), to Australia and is native to the Old World tropics. In some areas the butterfly occurs only as a migrant. In the neighbouring area of the Mediterranean region the species sometimes establishes colonies along the coasts of Croatia (Perković, 2006; Koren et al., 2019), Montenegro (Jakšić & Ristić, 1999), Albania (Luquet & Misja, 1989; Gaskin, 1990; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019; Nahirnić-Beshkova et al., 2022), Greece: mainland (Owen, 1991) and North Aegean Island of Lemnos (Langourov et al., 2021), but has also been recorded from other countries and areas nearby, e.g. Bosnia and Herzegovina (Koren & Kulijer, 2016); Turkey: Island of Gökçeada (Okyar & Aktaş, 2006) and east of the Black Sea – Russian Federation: Republic of Dagestan (Morgun & Ilyina, 2021), Azerbaijan (Christoph, 1886; Nekrutenko, 1990).

It is classified as a migrant from Group III Emigrants (Eitschberger et al., 1991).

The species is polyvoltine and prefers arid, bushy, rocky habitats, also encountered near gardens in cities and parks and cultivated areas (Tolman & Lewington, 1997). The larval host plants are mostly from family

Apocynaceae, especially *Asclepias* L., *Calotropis* R.Br., *Cynanchum acutum* L. (Gil-T., 2006; Koren et al., 2019; Galanos, 2022). The adult butterflies obtain nectar from various flowering plants.

The populations on the Balkans belong to the nominate subspecies – *Danaus chrysippus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Material and methods

The butterfly photos were taken by Nikolay Simov using a Samsung A256B/DSN camera. The maps were generated with QGIS 3.8 Zanzibar, Mac OS X version and Google Earth, online version.

Results and discussion

During a walk (sunny and warm (32°C) weather between 12:30–12:50 on 17 August) we noticed an interesting butterfly that flew out of a flower bed in the City Garden of Varna. A close look at the flying specimen convinced us that it was something different and much more interesting than the initial assumption that it was a migrating painted lady

Fig. 1. Map of Varna area, showing the location of *Danaus chrysippus*'s observation [satellite image] © Google, data attribution: imagery from 24.07.2023.

Fig. 2. *Danaus chrysippus* ♂ nectaring on *Jacobaea maritima* (L.) Pelser & Meijden, with the monument of Tsar Kaloyan in the back (photo: N. Simov).

Fig. 3. *Danaus chrysippus* ♂ nectaring on *Jacobaea maritima* (L.) Pelser & Meijden, 17 August 2025 (photo: N. Simov).

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butterfly, *Vanessa cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758). After waiting for it to land and start feeding, we were able to take a large number of photographs and be completely sure that this was the species *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

The exact data about the locality are: Bulgaria, Black Sea Coast, Varna, 43.20475°N; 27.91156°E; 17.08.2025, N. Simov, A. Georgieva, P. Dedov, M. Simov observed and photographed.

The butterfly actively fed for about 15 minutes on flowering *Jacobaea maritima* (L.) Pels & Meijden, used for landscaping in the City Garden of Varna. It was in no way attracted by the abundantly flowering *Hibiscus* sp. bushes in the vicinity.

Due to its reporting in surrounding countries, its discovery in our country is to some extent expected, it had to happen. The coasts of Black Sea, combined with various species of non-native plants growing in parks and gardens, have become a route north for some “exotic” terrestrial animals, including Lepidoptera, as shown at the beginning of the last century in the case of some species of Sphingidae (Buresch, 1926). Warm conditions and several mild winters could be a complement to this (Borgo et al., 1992). Although *Danaus chrysippus* can regularly cross large water or land areas, this is one of the possible migratory routes that led to the appearance of the species in our country.

It is worth mentioning that the find here also introduces a new subfamily, Danainae, and a new genus, *Danaus* Kluk, 1780, for the Bulgarian fauna.

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